

KINETICS OF PHASE TRANSFORMATIONS IN TI-TiB COMPOSITES CHARACTERISED USING HIGH ENERGY X-RAY DIFFRACTION

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1 Introduction

Titanium alloys reinforced with titanium monoboride (TiB) have been studied for more than 40 years [1]. The mechanical potential of this metal matrix composite was identified very early in its development, the material showing an interesting compromise between static properties (Young's modulus, yield and ultimate tensile strength), fatigue properties (low and high cycle), high temperature properties (creep), and wear behaviour [2]. Nevertheless, the material is today still not used in many applications, for several reasons: the cost of its development and of its production, the low ductility of the material produced with high levels of reinforcement and the difficulty in controlling the reinforcement formation, size and morphology. Despite this, as for TiC reinforcements in titanium alloys [3] [4], few applications can be found in the literature [6] [7], most of them for high-added value products [7] [8].

Inspired from the work from Saito et al. [6] [7], but also from others [9] [10] [11] [12], we've developed a powder metallurgy route to produce Ti-TiB ductile composites with relatively high levels of reinforcement [13]. The work presented here focuses mainly on one of the key points identified above in the development of this type of composite: the control of the TiB reinforcement formation, of its size and morphology. Indeed, despite the numerous publications on the Ti-TiB materials [2], the TiB formation is unclear. Several mechanisms have been proposed for the conversion of the boron precursor into the TiB [13] [14] [15], but controlling the TiB remains complicated. Furthermore, the processing route employed for this study requires mechanical alloying, which has been shown to have an important influence on the titanium alloys used as matrices for titanium matrix composites (notably important gas contaminations) [8] [9].

Using high energy X-ray diffraction, we have been able to characterise in-situ the transition of the

reinforcement from TiB₂ to TiB, during the high temperature treatments of the processing route. Moreover, we have been able to analyse the influence of the processing route and of the reinforcement on the titanium matrix, from a microstructural and phases transformations kinetics point of view.

2 Experimental Procedure

2.1 Raw Materials

ASTM Grade 5 (Ti-6Al-4V) was investigated, and used in powder form. The powders were produced by inert gas atomisation, and are approximately spherical (size distribution between 45-75 µm). TiB₂ ceramic powders (D₅₀ ≈ 4.8 µm) were used as a boron source for the TiB formation. The ceramic powders shape is irregular. Table 1 gives the typical composition of both powders.

2.2 Composite Preparation

TiB₂ powders were low energy mixed with the Ti-6Al-4V powders, to achieve a global composition of 12 wt% of TiB₂. Materion AMC's proprietary process of high energy mixing (known as mechanical alloying, hereafter called MA) was employed to prepare the composite powders. These powders were then poured into cans, degassed at elevated temperatures and the cans hermetically sealed. A Hot Isostatic Pressing (HIP) was carried out at 1193 K and 140 MPa for 2 h to achieve 100% of the theoretical density. The cans were then removed from the billets by machining. For the purpose of this study, some of the composite powders were also cold compacted in order to emphasise the TiB₂ to TiB transition. These powders were uniaxially cold compacted in an inert glove box, to avoid interstitial (oxygen, hydrogen and nitrogen) contamination in the powder compact.

2.2 Characterisation

An in situ high energy X-ray diffraction (HEXRD) was used to follow quantitatively the phase transformation kinetics during different heat treatments. This technique allows diffraction patterns to be recorded while heat treating the samples [17]. This way, phase amounts as well as mean cell parameters and Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) of diffraction peaks were determined for each identified phase. HEXRD experiments were performed at PETRA III storage-ring, situated at the DESY facility (Hamburg, Germany).

Fig. 1 shows the experimental set-up. The beam used had a wavelength of 0.124 Å. The samples were placed in an induction Bähr dilatometer, equipped with two windows allowing the beam in and out. This dilatometer was used as a furnace for heat treating the samples. A type S thermocouple was welded on the samples surface, close to the analysed volume, to accurately monitor the temperature. The complete Debye-Scherrer rings were recorded in transmission on a fast plate detector. The distance between the sample and the detector was 1.6 m, with an acquisition time estimated to be 3.5 s. The 2D diffraction rings were integrated using FIT2D program, to produce classical $I/2\theta$ diffraction patterns. They were finally analysed using Fullprof program, based on the Rietveld method.

Three different heat treatments were studied and are summarised in Table 2:

A. A simulation of the HIP thermal cycle was applied to the cold compacted powders. A temperature of 1193 K was applied for 2 h, with a heating and cooling rate of 0.25 K.s⁻¹. This was chosen to simulate process conditions used in industry.

B. A high temperature heat treatment, applied to the cold compacted powders. A temperature of 1573 K, applied for 0.3 h, was chosen based on the treatments found in the literature [12] [14], but also to be close or above the β transus temperature of the matrix. This temperature should be high enough to assure a complete conversion of the TiB₂ precursor into the final form of reinforcement, TiB. A high heating rate of 25 K.s⁻¹ was here chosen to limit the reaction during heating.

C. A high temperature heat treatment applied to the dense HIP'ed material. Again, the temperature chosen was 1573 K applied for 0.5 h, as this treatment is used to complete the conversion from

the TiB₂ to TiB after the compaction made at 1193 K for 2 h.

The microstructure of the materials at different steps of the process was also investigated. The samples were polished using a standard SiC papers polishing route, down to 4000 grit, and finished with an alumina suspension polishing solution. The samples were analysed on a FEI Quanta™, Field Emission Gun Scanning Electron Microscope (FEG-SEM), equipped with a secondary electron (SE) detector and a backscattered electron (BSE) detector.

3 Results

3.1 Initial material

3.1.1 Microstructure

Fig. 2a and 2b. show micrographs of the as-received titanium powders. The spherical shape of these powders is confirmed, although multiple satellites could be found attached to the powders. The high magnification micrograph in Fig. 2b. reveals the internal microstructure after solidification and rapid transformation in the solid state. This microstructure is made of an acicular morphology of α (maybe α'). This is typical of the rapidly solidified alloys. α' is formed when rapidly cooling down from the β phase field by a martensitic transformation process. It has a hexagonal crystal structure, similar to the α phase, but with the same composition as the β phase [19].

Fig. 2c displays the morphology of the TiB₂ powders, confirming its angular and irregular morphology. Fig. 2d and 2e show the composite powders after the MA process. It shows their important coarsening during MA, the composite powders being now bigger than 100 μm for most of them. Fig. 2e displays the microstructure of the MA'ed powders. The TiB₂ reinforcement is grey and the titanium matrix is white. The distribution of the TiB₂ reinforcement in these powders is homogeneous, although it is still possible to identify isolated areas of unreinforced regions. It also shows the very deformed aspect of the material; this is as a result of the cold fracture and welding processes which occur during the MA process. Also, MA is very energetic and massively deforming ductile materials like titanium, explaining this microstructure. This microstructure is comparable with the ones produced by Godfrey et al.[10].

Fig. 2f and 2g represents BSE micrographs of the material after HIPing. The mechanically alloyed

structure shows regions of lower reinforcement content, corresponding to that of the initial powder size. Although the majority of the structure is homogeneous, regions of lower reinforcement are present due to the nature of MA process, which is optimised for aluminium systems rather than Ti-based materials. The microstructure of the matrix is globular α , with a small amount of β observed between the α grains. A difference can be seen between the reinforced and the unreinforced regions: the α grains are equiaxed in both cases, but in the reinforced regions, the size of the grains is very small ($<1 \mu\text{m}$) compared to the unreinforced regions where the grains are larger ($>1 \mu\text{m}$). Fig. 2g also shows that the reaction between the TiB_2 and the matrix to form TiB has begun. This reaction has been studied already [15] [16] [17] [18] and is known to produce titanium monoboride (TiB). The reaction produces here three morphologies of reinforcement after the HIP:

- very small TiB needles dispersed in the matrix, in grey in the micrographs. The diameter of these needles does not exceed 500 nm,
- some TiB_2 remaining, which has not reacted yet, in black in the micrographs,
- at the former interface between the matrix and the TiB_2 particles, a zone of dense TiB is formed.

3.1.2 X-ray diffraction characterisation

The high energy X-ray diffraction patterns were recorded at ambient temperature for both the MA'ed powders and the HIP'ed composite. Fig. 3 represents the corresponding $I/2\theta$ diffraction patterns.

Two phases can be identified in the MA'ed powders:

- 88 wt% of a compact hexagonal phase (α or α'), with $a=2.93 \text{ \AA}$ and $c=4.67 \text{ \AA}$ for the mean lattice parameters,
- 12 wt% TiB_2 (space group: P6/mmm), with $a=3.03 \text{ \AA}$ and $c=3.23 \text{ \AA}$.

The X-ray diffraction confirms that the reaction between the TiB_2 and the matrix has not started yet after mechanical alloying. No β phase can be detected. However, it is interesting to note here that the mean lattice parameter for the α after MA is the same as the one found in the literature for Ti-6Al-4V [19].

Five different phases can be identified in the HIP'ed composite:

- 85 wt% of α (or α') with $a=2.93 \text{ \AA}$ and $c=4.68 \text{ \AA}$,
- 1.5 wt% of β (BCC) with $a=3.21 \text{ \AA}$,
- 1 wt% of TiB_2 , with $a=3.03 \text{ \AA}$ and $c=3.23 \text{ \AA}$,

- 11.5 wt% of the TiB-B_f phase (space group: Cmc_m, hereafter called B_f), with $a=3.26 \text{ \AA}$, $b=8.46 \text{ \AA}$ and $c=3.04 \text{ \AA}$,

- 1 wt% of the TiB-B27 phase (space group: Pnma, hereafter called B27), with $a=6.11 \text{ \AA}$, $b=3.05 \text{ \AA}$ and $c=4.55 \text{ \AA}$.

Table 3 summarises the phase proportion and lattice parameters found for the different materials. X-ray diffraction analysis reveals that the reaction between TiB_2 and matrix has begun during the HIP. This reaction is producing two forms of TiB: the B27, which is the standard and stable form of titanium monoboride [22], and the B_f , which has been mainly identified in the past in TiAl intermetallics, and has been qualified as a metastable phase [23]. Regarding the matrix, after HIPing, it is still composed mainly of the α phase, but small amount of β (1.5 wt%) can be identified.

3.2 In situ characterisation

3.2.1 Experiment A: HIP Simulation

Fig. 4 shows some of the diffraction patterns recorded during experiment A and Fig. 5 represents the cumulated phase amounts evolution during the treatment.

The $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ transformation starts around 873 K. The amount of β phase increases with the increasing temperature, to reach a maximum of 17 wt% at 1193 K. During the dwell, the amount of α slightly increases again, consuming the β . The composite contains 15 wt% of β and 71 wt% of α after the 2 h at 1193 K.

The reaction between the TiB_2 and the matrix seems to start around 973 K. Indeed, at this temperature, B_f phase can be clearly identified and the TiB_2 peaks begin to lower. At this temperature, the B27 is not present. When the dwelling temperature is attained, the TiB formation is well advanced (12.5 wt% of B_f and 0.5 wt% of B27), the TiB_2 peaks are rather low in intensity (2.5 wt%). After two hours at 1193 K, the reaction continues, but very slowly. The TiB formed is mainly composed of the B_f form, as only limited quantities of B27 can be detected. At the end of the dwell, the reinforcement is composed of 0.5 wt% of TiB_2 , 12.5 wt% of B_f and 1.5 wt% of B27. The diffraction pattern corresponding to the powders at ambient temperature after this experiment more or less correspond to the HIP'ed material pattern, in Fig. 3b.

Fig. 6 represents the evolution of the FWHM for the $\{101\}$ plans of the α phase, during experiment A. It shows the important thinning of the peaks for this phase, between 473 K and 1073 K. Both during the

dwell at 1193 K and the cooling down, this value remains stable. This peak thinning is particularly important for this phase. For the borides, FWHM is much lower than for the α phase and remains constant during the heat treatment (0.04° for the TiB₂ for example).

3.2.2 Experiment B: high temperature treatment on the powders

Fig. 7 represents the phase amounts during experiment B. They are given mainly for temperatures above 1193 K, temperature used for the HIP, as the reactions occurring before are very similar to the ones found in experiment A. The only difference is a slight increase in the temperature where the reactions begin ($\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ transformation and TiB₂ conversion), this is explained by the high heating rate used compared to experiment A, but this difference is small.

The reactions observed during experiment A are continuing when the temperature is increasing. For the matrix, the $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ transformation continues. When the temperature reaches 1573 K, there is about 5 wt% of α and 77 wt% of β . The α amount reduces until the end of the dwell (1 wt%).

Regarding the reinforcement, the conversion from TiB₂ to the titanium monoborides seems to start around 1103 K. The monoboride formed is the B_f. At the beginning of the dwell, there are only 4 wt% of TiB₂ left in the composite. 14 wt% of B_f have been formed, whereas the composite contains only 1 wt% of B27 at this stage. After 5 min at 1573 K, there is no TiB₂ left in the material. The level of B_f remains stable, whereas more B27 is formed. Afterwards, the level of B27 keeps on increasing, at the expense of the B_f. At the end of the dwell, the material contains 1 wt% of B_f and 23 wt% of B27.

For this heat treatment on the powders, the FWHM for the different phases evolves in the same way as for experiment A.

3.2.3 Experiment C: high temperature treatment on HIP'ed composite

Fig. 8 represents the evolution of the phase amounts during the heat treatment made on the HIP'ed composite at elevated temperature. The $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ transformation starts around 873 K, as for cold compacted powders. When the dwell temperature is reached (1573 K), the matrix is fully β .

The amount of TiB₂ (1 wt%) decreases starting at 1373 K, showing that the reaction between the diboride and the matrix further progresses. The quantity of B_f remains constant until 1473 K, but

begins to decrease at 1573 K. On the contrary, the B27 phase begins to increase when the dwell starts. This amount is progressively increasing at the expense of the B_f. The final amounts of reinforcement at the end of the dwell are 2 wt% of B_f and 20 wt% of B27.

During the cooling, the α formation starts between 1573 K and 1473 K. The amount of α progressively increase to reach 71 wt% at 873 K, and remains constant until ambient temperature. The final phase amounts of the material, as well as the final mean lattice parameter are given in Table 3. The final reinforcement level found is 1 wt% of B_f and 21 wt% of B27, level which is quite similar to the one found at the end of the dwell, but also to the one at the end of the experiment B.

3.3. Final microstructure

Fig. 2h and 2i. displays the final microstructure of the composite, after experiment C, i.e. the heat treatment for 0.5 h at 1573 K. The distribution of the reinforcement seems homogeneous. It is composed of needles, which have grown in the matrix. The apparent needle size characterised in 2D is up to 30 μm for the length, and 3 μm for the diameter. These needles are one order of magnitude bigger than the ones found in the composite after the HIP. (Fig. 2g and Fig. 2i)

The matrix is composed of α grains, with a fairly nodular shape. The β phase is present between these nodules.

4 Discussion

4.1 TiB₂ \rightarrow TiB conversion reaction

The different experiments are showing the kinetics of the conversion from the titanium diboride (TiB₂) to the titanium monoboride (TiB). The process used to produce the composite is particular, and has not been often studied in the literature [2] [10] [24]. The experiment made on the cold compacted powders shows that no reaction begins during MA, even if this type of high energy mixing is known to produce heat [25]. This heat is not high enough to begin a reaction.

The reaction between the TiB₂ and the matrix begins at approximately 973 K. This reaction produces one type of TiB, called TiB-B_f. This form of titanium boride has already been identified in various types of materials, and is also common for other metals boride (V, Cr, Ni, Nb... [23]). It has been mainly identified in the Ti-Al intermetallics previously [20]

[21], but also in some cases of laser claddings of the same system, Ti-6Al-4V + TiB [27]. In all cases, the composite goes through a liquid state phase, and, to the authors knowledge, it is the first time that the B_f has been identified in a composite produced by a solid state route. This B_f form has been qualified in the literature as metastable, as it seems to evolve in the more ordinary form of monoboride (the TiB-B27) after prolonged heat treatments at high temperature [23]. This character seems to be confirmed here. The B_f is the first phase formed in the reaction of the TiB_2 with the matrix, but further evolves to form small amounts of the B27 phase after the 2 h at 1193 K, and higher quantities after 0.5 h at 1573 K.

The conversion reaction ($TiB_2 \rightarrow Ti-B_f$) is very fast. With experiment B (heating rate of $25 \text{ K}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$), the reaction begun at 1103 K, and at 1573 K, there is almost no TiB_2 left. The passing from one form of monoboride to the other is slower. At the lower dwell temperature (1193 K), a small amount of B27 is formed during the dwell (1.5 wt%). For the higher temperature heat treatment, the kinetics of B27 formation is accelerated, and begins during the heating stage for both treatments (B and C). It can be emphasised that this acceleration occurs as the amount of α is rather low (approx. 10 wt% in each case).

The conversion reaction of TiB_2 particles included in a titanium matrix has been studied in the past [14] [15] [21] [16]. It is known to produce massive TiB at the interface between the TiB_2 particle and the matrix, with the reaction front moving inward, free boron moving outward, and TiB needles forming in the matrix. Considering that one mole of TiB_2 will produce one mole of TiB and one mole of free boron, and that the solubility of the boron in titanium is limited (reported to be <1at% both in α and in β [28] [29]), the matrix will be rapidly saturated in boron. The question is then to know whether this free boron moving outward will form directly needles at the former interface between the TiB_2 and the matrix [14], and/or will be able to nucleate further away from the boron source, in appropriate sites, due to a supersaturation of the matrix in boron [30].

Our present results show that after the HIP treatment (Fig. 2f and Fig. 2g), some TiB_2 is still observed, with an outer rim of massive TiB and fine TiB needles (500 nm max. for the diameter) inhomogeneously distributed in the matrix. At this state, the major phases present are TiB_2 (0.5 wt%) and the B_f (12.5 wt%). One can assume therefore

that the small needles as well as the outer rime could be associated mainly with the B_f . Moreover, as the matrix is mainly composed of α phase (70 wt% during the dwell) one can consider that the B_f forms preferably in this phase. After the dwell at 1575 K, the reinforcement phase is mainly large needles (Fig. 2h and Fig. 2i). The distribution of these needles is much more homogeneous than the ones observed after HIP. This structure can correspond to the B27, as this phase is the major one detected after the given treatment.

4.2 Matrix transformation kinetics

For the three experiments, the matrix has shown the same transformation kinetics. $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ transformation begins around 873 K. For experiment A, this transformation continues up to the dwell, but turns over after 0.5 h, and the α phase begins to grow again. As this treatment is applied on cold compacted powders, the surface oxidation might be relevant, despite the vacuum furnace used. The increase in the amount of α at the expense of β might therefore correspond to the growth of some “ α case”. For the two other experiments, the α dissolution continues with the increasing temperature. A difference can nevertheless be spotted between the two treatments: when 1573 K is reached, there is some α remaining in the matrix for experiment B, whereas it has all been dissolved in the case of experiment C. The difference in heating rate could explain this modification. The heating rate for experiment B was chosen to be very high to limit the borides conversion during the heat up, but this may also influence the dissolution process, explaining the α still remaining at such temperature.

However, it is interesting to note here that for both experiments, the $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ transformation domain has been extended compared to a standard Ti-6Al-4V. Previous experiments have shown that the dissolution of the α phase starts around 873 K for a β transus around 1268 K for Ti-6Al-4V [31]. Here, the same temperature was found for the beginning of the allotropic transformation. But the temperature at which nearly no more α phase is present for the studied composite is 1548 K for $0.25 \text{ K}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and 1573 K for $25 \text{ K}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. Considering that for heating rate of $0.25 \text{ K}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, we are not too far from equilibrium; this would mean an increase of the transus temperature of more than 200 K. Several explanations could be given for this shift:

- A modification in the alloying elements levels in the matrix. On one hand, one could argue that the Ti of the matrix consumed to produce the

TiB increases the relative levels of alloying elements in the matrix (aluminium and vanadium). This may modify the transformation kinetics in the matrix. If we consider an alloy with a perfect composition of 6 wt% of aluminium and 4 wt% of vanadium, the titanium consumption will lead to a final composition of 6.18 and 4.12 wt% of V and Al respectively. On the other hand, it has been found that in this type of alloys, alloying elements may have a different behaviour toward the borides. The solubility of aluminium in TiB is almost null, whereas up to 3.3 wt% of V has been found in the TiB [30] [31]. This might lead to a decrease in the beta stabiliser (vanadium) in Ti-6Al-4V, with a corresponding increase in the β transus. Taking the same perfect alloy, with exactly 6 wt% of Al and 4 wt% of V, and taking into account the amount of Ti used to produce the TiB, the vanadium solubility in TiB would lead to a final composition of Ti-6.18Al-3.88V for the matrix. The increase in alpha stabiliser and the decrease in beta stabiliser elements will necessarily lead to an increase of the transus temperature, but the slight modification calculated here can't be accounted for the whole shift of the transus temperature.

- Despite its very low solubility, the boron introduced in the matrix might also have an influence on the transus temperature. The boron is reported to be alpha stabiliser [34]. In equilibrium systems, its influence has been evaluated going up to 30 K on the transus temperature [35].

- There might be some oxygen and nitrogen contamination during different processing steps of the process. Godfrey [18] attributed the changes in the transus temperature to pickups of these two elements during the MA. The MA is made under inert atmosphere, but pickups are still possible. One could also imagine small amounts of air remaining after degassing at elevated temperature, recombining with the material during the HIP. Gas pickups is the phenomena the more likely to have an important influence on the transus temperature, as their effect is relatively strong [19]. It also has to be noted that the gas levels in the TiB₂ powders used is non-negligible, and has to be taken into account for the gas contamination of the matrix.

For all treatments, the presence of α' after a slow cooling has to be excluded, as this phase is only formed when rapidly quenching from the β domain. The presence of this phase in the gas atomised powders and in the MA'ed powders can be assumed,

especially with the absence of β in the MA'ed powders. But as the peaks for the α' phase merge with the ones of the α phase in X-ray diffraction, it can't be confirmed yet.

The FWHM has been calculated for all phases during the different heat treatments. A strong variation was only observed for one phase, i.e. the α phase, when the treatment is applied to the MA'ed powders. The FWHM is dependant on both the instrumentation used (instrumental broadening) and the material itself. Two parameters of the material can broaden the peaks: the size of the coherent domains, corresponding more or less to the size of the grains, and the internal stresses. We've shown in Ti-3Al-2.5V matrix composites the important reduction of the size of the titanium grains after MA (\varnothing 10 nm crystallites) [13]. The same behaviour could be expected, on the MA'ed Ti-6Al-4V matrix composite powders. The important reduction of the FWHM during the heat up can be therefore attributed to the coarsening of the matrix grains. However, the massive plastic deformation applied to the powders during mechanical alloying could also lead to important internal stresses in the material. Therefore, these stresses could also be partly responsible of the peak broadening in the diffraction patterns of the MA'ed composite powders. The stresses being relaxed with the temperature increasing, this would also explain the thinning of the diffraction peaks while heat treating the material.

5 Conclusion

The in-situ characterisation of the TiB reinforced titanium matrix composites using high energy X-ray diffraction allowed a characterisation of the kinetics of phase transformations in the material. The main conclusions are:

- The transition from TiB₂ to TiB-B27, via the TiB-B_f metastable phase. The B_f is the first phase formed during the conversion, but progressively transforms into the B27 stable boride during elevated temperature heat treatments.

- The modification of the phase transformation kinetics and of the β transus temperature, mainly due to the process used to manufacture the composite and to the nature of the composite itself. The transus temperature has been found near 1548 K.

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Fig. 1. Experimental set-up for the in-situ recording of the diffraction rings during the heat treatments applied to the composite samples

Table 1. Typical compositions (in weight %) and characteristics of the powders used to prepare the composites.

Material	Shape	Size	Al	V	B	Fe	C	O	N	Ti
Ti-6Al-4V	Spherical	45-75 μm	5.9	3.9	-	0.19	0.01	0.12	0.01	Bal
TiB ₂	Irregular	-10 μm	-	-	30	0.1	0.5	1.1	0.6	Bal

Table 2. The different experiments applied to the composite.

Experiment	Material	Heating rate (K.s ⁻¹)	Dwelling temp. (K)	Dwelling time (h)	Cooling Rate (K.s ⁻¹)
A	Cold compacted powders	0.25	1193	2	0.25
B	Cold compacted powders	25	1573	0.3	10
C	HIP'ed material	0.25	1573	0.5	0.25

Fig. 2. SE and BSE micrographs of the material at different steps of the process: a. and b. gas atomised Ti-6Al-4V powders (SE), c. TiB_2 powders (SE), d. composite powders after MA (SE), e. internal structure of a composite powder (BSE), f. and g. the composite after HIPing (BSE), h. and i. the composite after experiment C.

Fig. 3. $I/2\theta$ diffraction pattern and the corresponding diffraction plans, for a. the MA'ed powders, b. the as HIP'ed composite.

Table 3. Summary of the phases identified at different steps of the processing route, the amount estimated for each phase, and lattice parameters. Literature values for lattice parameters are given for comparison.

	Material	Source/State	Phase	Wt%	Lattice parameters (Å)		
					a	b	c
References	Ti-6Al-4V	[19]	α	-	2.93	2.93	4.67
			β	-	3.19	3.19	3.19
	Titanium Borides	[36]	TiB ₂	-	3.03	3.03	3.23
		[21]	TiB-B _f	-	3.23	8.56	3.05
		[22]	TiB-B27	-	6.11	3.05	4.56
This study	Ti-6Al-4V+12 wt% TiB ₂	MA'ed powders	α (or α')	88	2.93	2.93	4.67
			TiB ₂	12	3.03	3.03	3.23
	Ti-6Al-4V+12 wt% TiB ₂	HIP'ed composite	α	85	2.93	2.93	4.68
			β	1.5	3.21	3.21	3.21
			TiB ₂	1	3.03	3.03	3.23
			TiB-B _f	11.5	3.26	8.46	3.04
	Ti-6Al-4V+12 wt% TiB ₂	HIP'ed and heat treated composite	α	72	2.93	2.93	4.69
			β	6	3.22	3.22	3.22
			TiB-B _f	1	3.23	8.56	3.05
			TiB-B27	21	6.11	3.05	4.56

Fig. 4. Diffraction patterns of the Ti-6Al-4V + 12wt.% TiB₂ composite powders at different temperatures during heating up and after 2 hours dwelling at 1193 K (Experiment A).

Fig. 5. In situ evolution of the phase amounts during experiment A.

Fig. 6. Evolution of the FWHM for the {101} peaks of the α phase, during experiment A.

Fig. 7. In situ evolution of the phase amounts during experiment B.

Fig. 8. In situ evolution of the phase amounts during experiment C.

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